

LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL ASPECTS OF LEXICAL UNITS IN LITERARY TRANSLATION (ON THE EXAMPLE OF TRANSLATIONS OF THE STORY “SUCH IS LIFE”)

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***Abstract.** In this article, the ideas about the concepts of artistic translation, linguistic culture, and lexical meaning are thoroughly studied. The specific characteristics of lexical units with linguistic and cultural characteristics used in the short story "Such is Life" translated from Uzbek into English, expressed in the original and translated texts translation analysis are illustrated through several examples. An explanation of the examples seen in the study, as well as, in some cases, equivalent lexical units specific to the translated text is recommended. This article provides detailed information about the importance of a thorough study of language units in translation in the process of linguistic and cultural analysis.*

***Keywords:** literary translation, linguistic culture, alternative, lexical units, literary novels, linguistic units, language tools.*

At the stage of scientific-technical, cultural and economic development, a foreign language is widely used as a means of oral and written communication between representatives of different peoples around the world. Due to the development of modern technologies, today scientists from different countries of the world have the opportunity to quickly exchange information and conduct joint research, and thanks to these means of communication, modern science is achieving unprecedented results. In such conditions, the need for high-quality translation of scientific literature of many production organizations is increasing significantly. Translators must constantly add translations of scientific literature to their vocabulary and regularly increase their ability to understand terms and their meanings.

The art of translation plays an important role in the development of the world's culture and transfers all the charm and culture of one language to another one [1,28]. In case, it is a literary translation, it requires more inspiration and effort from the translator. Linguistic culture is the basis of literary translation. When talking about translation and literary translation itself, it is necessary to mention its origin and the definitions given to this word. “The first theoretical ideas about translation originated in ancient Rome”, - says Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor M. Kholbekov in his article published in “World Literature” magazine [14]. Aristotle, Cicero, and Horace, who knew Greek and Latin languages perfectly, expressed the opinion that it is not appropriate to follow the sequence of words in the process of translation and that it is better to weigh their expressions first and then translate them. Later, Bartolommeo and Manetti in Italy, du Belle and Malherbe in France, Bacon and Dryden in England, Goethe and Humboldt in Germany, and Lomonosov and Sumarokov in Russia expressed their theoretical understandings of translation. Until the 20th century, the word “translation” acquired a certain meaning and was used only for the translation of historical, philosophical and literary works, and about an oral translator it was called “tilmoch” in Turkish, “tolmach” in Slavic, “dolmetschen” in German, “interpreter”

in English and French. Translation is derived from the word translator, and translator is derived from the Persian word tarzaban [14,6].

Literary translation is a broader concept than language translation and includes the translation of historical experiences, specific worldviews, and cultures into another language. Historical and modern linguistic facts are analyzed through the prism of spiritual culture in linguistic and cultural studies. In this regard, one can see different results from V.N.Teleya's scientific research in V.A. Maslova's concept. In particular, the issues of synchronic and diachronic are also investigated in linguocultural studies [2,42]. In addition, literary translation is the process of translating poetic, dramatic and prose works into other foreign languages. It helps to develop student's understanding of the world and its history, philosophy, and politics. While we are talking about what literary translation is, it should be emphasized that it is a type of translation that requires a creative approach and translation skills from the translator. Literary translation constitutes the translation of:

1. Fiction novels.
2. Literary articles.
3. Plays.
4. Poems.
5. Novels.
6. Songs.
7. Epics.
8. Stories and others.

In recent years, the issues of language and culture began to be studied in the Linguoculturology in detail. According to V.V.Vorobev, -"Today, linguocultural science is a method that studies a set of cultural values selected in a certain way, investigates the lively communicative processes of speech creation and perception, the linguistic experience of a person and the national mentality, systematically gives a linguistic picture of the world view and provides an education that can be noted as a new philological science that ensures the fulfilment of educational and intellectual tasks. Therefore, linguocultural science is a complex science that reflects the interaction and influence of culture and language and this process as a whole structure of linguistic and non-linguistic (cultural) units [7,14].

Linguistic culture embodies not only the lifestyle of each nation today but also their national traditions, artistic, and scientific culture, music, literature, artistic image, architecture, theatre, cinematography, and lifestyle, which have been preserved for centuries. Every communication or original message has practical value. The interpreter must know whether the message is a statement of facts, a suggestion, an order, or a joke. For example, "I don't know" (hold) is not only translated as a statement but can also mean hesitation ("Let's see"). "What gives" - American slang for "How are things?" gives the content of the question. Translation is the process of transferring a message across linguistic and cultural barriers [6,28]. For Uzbek linguistic culture, it is normal to compare women's faces to the moon, or apple, sometimes to a Kaiser roll bread, in English to a cherry, or rose (as red as a cherry/rose), in Chinese and Korean to an apricot, a willow branch. In China and Korea, women are happy when they are compared to snakes. Because, in these linguistic cultures, the snake is a symbol of wisdom, beauty and dexterity. The same concept can be reflected in different linguistic cultures using different means of expression, that is, using different analogical standards. For example, the Uzbeks compare strong people to elephants, and

the English compare them to horses: Uzbeks liken people who work tirelessly to ants, and Turkish – to bees (ari gibi) [6,32].

Lexical units, that is, words, phrases and phraseological units, are the basic elements of language, which express specific meanings in their cultural context. To understand properly and translate these units in literary translation, a thorough study of their cultural context is necessary. The lexical meaning of a word or lexical unit can be considered as its specific value in a certain language system and the “place” it occupies in this system through its use [8,12]. Each word differs from other lexical units by its lexical meaning. The only condition for the translation to be created by the original in terms of content and form is the selective expression of suitable lexical means by the translator in his language. This responsibility depends on him, first of all, to fully understand the original meaning and function, and then to express the thought fully formed in his memory based on the culture and standards of his native language.

Language tools are not only abstracted from their material and logical meanings and acquired emotional-affective and artistic-aesthetic (figurative) meanings and signs in the artistic discourse, but also remain in their initial meanings in the context of ordinary communication. Even when they are used, the translator faces several practical difficulties regarding the correct selection of the necessary linguistic tools [9,71]. For example, English “for” and its Russian dictionary equivalent “ради” prepositions are given in Uzbek as “uchun” in all dictionaries, and in most textual situations one of them easily replaces the other. But the preposition “for” (ради) in the sentence “Well, I’ll do it for you” [JA, 188] used in M. Twain’s novel “Janna d’Ark” does not have the “use” characteristic of the auxiliary “for” without reflecting the sign of meaning, it acquires an additional sign of meaning, such as “for the sake of”, which is not reflected in the dictionary, so that the translator, who has seen that the use of “for” here cannot ensure adequacy, the original meaning chooses the combination “for the sake of his face” that can clearly express his name.

Так и быть, сделаю это ради вас - ЖА, 151 // На. mayli, sening yuzi-xotiring uchun shunday qilaman - JA, 140 [9,71].

It is known that each national culture has its characteristics, which show intercultural differences, that is, different aspects, and cause difficulties for the translator in the process of translation. Speaking about O‘tkir Hashimov’s short story “Dunyoning ishlari” (“Such is life”) first of all, it should be noted that the short story is simple and popular. Therefore, it was translated into foreign languages, including English. There are two different versions of the story translated directly from Uzbek to English by O. Mominov, I. Tokhtasinov, as well as Abdullah Roziyev and Mark Reese. Comparing the translated English versions with the original work, we observe the expression of nationality in the story:

Original:	Ko‘rdingmi, yaxshi o‘smay qolgan. Yetimlarga rahm qilish kerak [4].
English translation: O. Mominov, I. Tokhtasinov	You see, it is smaller than others; we must take care of orphans [5].
English translation: A. Roziyev, Mark Reese	You see, it could not grow properly. Mercy should be shown about orphans [3].

Originally, the verb “rahm qilmoq” expresses humanity, and in the first English translation, the phraseological unit to look after someone or something, take care of, was chosen as an equivalent. The original and translated versions of the phrase “rahm qilmoq” and “take care” are in harmony with the idea of educating the young generation, which has become the main policy of our country, because, through this, a sense of humanity is formed in young people. In this case, it can be seen that the sentence that *did not grow well* in the translation of O. Mominov and I. Tokhtasinov was translated into Uzbek through an English sentence that gives meaning *smaller than the others*. At this time, it can be seen that the translation of A. Roziyev and Mark Reese are translated with a sentence that gives the meaning that it is *not well developed*. That is, the sentence is delivered through a sentence that has happened up to this day and gives the meaning of the past tense. Also, in the interpretation of O. Mominov and I. Tokhtasinov, the continuation of the sentence seems like a mother giving appropriate advice only for her child and herself, while in the translation of A. Roziyev and M. Riz, it is a call to all humanity by passing the sentence in the passive voice. We believe that it represents the meaning and is translated much closer to the original.

Original:	Gazetachining ishi bir tomondan uloqchi otga, ikkinchi tomondan omoch tortadigan otga o‘xshaydi. Uloqchi otddek manzilga yuguradi-yu, yer haydaydigan otddek har kuni omoch tortadi... [4].
English translation: O. Mominov, I. Tokhtasinov	The work of the newspaper editor resembles two horses: horse in the “uloq” (national competition which is organized with horses) and a horse of a plow. He runs to the address like a horse in a “uloq” and ploughs land like a horse of plow... [5].
English translation: A. Roziyev, Mark Reese	In many ways the image of a racehorse best suits the job of a newspaper editor. Yet we might also appear like the draft horse left to plow fields in the country. We rush to a deadline like a racehorse, yet drag along like the honey in the field... [3].

The highlighted journalist is compared to a horse in the “uloq”, which means that he always does all the work with agility, while the fact that he is compared to a plough horse means that his work is hard. In the translation of O. Mominov and I. Tokhtasinov, “uloqchi” horse is expressed as a horse in Uloq, the word Uloq is transliterated and the national color in the context is preserved. But we cannot say so about the second version of translation, because “uloqchi” horse is given in English translation as a racehorse. However, the word “racehorse” is translated into Uzbek as “racing horse”. Horse racing is an equestrian sport known almost all over the world, but uloq, ko’pkari is one of the ancient mass, national games of the peoples of Central Asia [10]. It seems that the translators have moved away from the original unit representing the national culture as a result of choosing an English equivalent.

Let's look at one more example of nationalism.

Original:	Oyim kun chiqmasdan turib yo‘laklarni supurardi. Biz aka-ukalar suv sepamiz. [4].
English translation: O. Mominov, I. Tokhtasinov	Mother would sweep the passages in the early dawn. We, brothers, watered the street [5].

English translation: A. Roziyev, Mark Reese	Before sunrise, she would sweep the streets. We brothers would help by sprinkling water on the ground [3].
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Uzbek people have a habit of getting up early in the morning, sweeping the yard and sidewalks, and sprinkling water, and they believe that blessing will enter the house with this. In the translation of O. Mominov and I. Tokhtasinov, the verb to sprinkle water is expressed by the English verb water, which in turn is closer to the meaning of watering. A. Roziyev and Mark Reese interpreted this word as a very successful equivalent. A sprinkle is a light fall of something, usually water. This is also a verb that means to spread something gently [11]. This, in turn, helped to express the custom of gently sprinkling water on the streets typical of Uzbek people, as well as to fully reflect the linguistic and cultural characteristics.

In conclusion, it should be said that when we talk about the linguistic and cultural approach in literary translation, we mean to translate the original text into the translated text as completely and accurately as possible. But any text will have linguistic specificity. If the translator cannot apply these methods and directions in the translation, the alternative will not be preserved in the translation and it will become the translator's creative work. Therefore, translators must translate texts using full translation methods and techniques. The place of linguistic culture is extremely important in literary translation. In general, without the skills and knowledge specific to the language and culture, the translator cannot achieve the expected result. It is natural. However, taking into account the linguistic and cultural aspects of lexical units in literary translation is necessary for success in translation. Interpreters play a key role in creating bridges between cultures because they transfer not only words but also cultural concepts. Success in translation depends on the correct understanding of the linguistic and cultural aspects of lexical units and their adaptation.

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